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APPOSITIONS IN THE CONTEMPORARY LINGUISTIC CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT:

THE APPOSITE UNIT (APPOSITION) - THIS IS THE ONE THAT PROVIDE A MORE EXPLICIT LINGUISTIC INTERPRETATION. IN THE CASE OF ANY APPOSITION, A SERIES OF CHANGES OCCUR, BECAUSE IT DENOTES THE EVALUATION OR RE-EVALUATION BY THE SPEAKER OF A FORMULATION, OF A PREVIOUS INFORMATION. IN OTHER WORDS, THE APPOSITION IS A PART OF A SENTENCE THAT EXPRESSES AN IDENTITY TO BE UNDERSTOOD WITH THE TERM OF REFERENCE EXPLAINED OR A QUALIFICATION, A CLASSIFICATION OF THE OBJECT NAMED BY HIM, IN A CIRCUMSTANCE GIVEN BY THE SPEAKER; IT IS A SECOND EXPRESSION OF THE SAME CONTENT, POSSESSED BY A CERTAIN TERM.

KEYWORDS: SYNTACTIC STRUCTURE, IDENTITY, APPOSITIVE RELATION, ACTANTIAL CONSTRUCTION, VALENCE, SEMANTIC.

The notion of apposition comes from the Latin *appositio*, meaning side by side, which shows that the apposition arose from the need to render a certain kind of connection of the words in the sentence. Despite the fact that this is known to the all authors, the definition of the apposition differs from one to another, each bringing its own particularity. In the tradition of Romanian grammar, the apposition is defined as “a species of the noun or pronominal attribute that determines a noun with which it has the same reference (The city of Bucharest is the capital of Romania) or a substitute of the noun: pronoun (You, his colleagues, know him better) or numeral (Out of the whole group of students came only two: Ionescu or Popescu)”. The apposition was also defined as a “noun attribute placed in the nominative case, regardless of the case of the determined term, or granted in the case thereof.” Beyond these definitions is the statement that “the syntactic structure of the apposition gives the impression that the syntactic connection between it and its noun is very weak, or that the apposition does not depend on its noun as the secondary part of the sentence on the corresponding main part.” In the specialty literature it has been stated that the apposition “is the part of the sentence that isolated, which resumes, clarifies, explains and specifies the content of the term to which it refers or qualifies, classifies the object named by this term, regardless of the lexical-grammatical class and the case and with which, logically, it is on the same plane. In other words, the apposition is a part of a sentence that expresses an identity to

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be understood with the term of reference explained or a qualification, a classification of the object named by him, in a circumstance given by the speaker; it is a second expression of the same content, possessed by a certain term.”

It is considered that the apposition resembles the parts of the sentence repeated (the subject, the direct and the indirect object), but it is also distinguished: the subject differs by content and by the fact that the latter is expressed only by the accentuated forms of the third person of the personal pronoun in N, but through a different topic. The resumed object is also distinguished by its content and the complement is expressed by the unaccented accusative and dative forms of the third person of the personal or reflexive pronom.

THE UNITS OF THE APPOSITIVE RELATION

“The appositive relation is a special type of relation, of discursive equivalence, which is constituted between two coreferential linguistic sequences - base (on the first position) and the apposition (on the second position): Only you can command them to sleep, / only you, / My brother in vain, / You, / In search of the bridegroom, / Who covers your ears with the wing. (A. Blandiana, The death in the light).

The appositive base can be expressed by different grammatical categories, such as:

- nouns: The soloist, Ioana, is my colleague.
- numerals (collective, ordinal, cardinal) – Both, Vasile and Vladut, are brothers.
- Three, Ioana, Elena and Costi, succeeded at the Olympiad.
- pronoun - He, Gigel, is my friend. That one, the student, hasn't finished his work.

The apposite unit (apposition) - this is the one that provide a more explicit linguistic interpretation. In the case of any apposition, a series of changes occur, because it denotes the evaluation or re-evaluation by the speaker of a formulation, of a previous information. The speaker changes his position with that of the interlocutor, analyzing his own speech, which may be ambiguous or insufficient in terms of information, as a result of which, the speaker launches a broader information, with the necessary details, thus avoiding possible confusion: Mr. President, Barack Obama, will pay a visit to Romania.

The apposition, like the appositive base, can be expressed by different nouns/nominals:

- nouns – I saw the painter, Dan.
- qualifying adjectives - The students, the boys, were at the football.
- numerals - Irina and Dorel, two, will go to the camp.
 - Dana, the fourth, will stay home.
 - Dorin and Gigel, both, passed on in the next stage.
- pronoun – Irina, she is innocent. His brother, that one, left.
- verbs to infinitive: gerund, participle or supine:
 - It started to scream, that is, to shout louder at her.
 - By always pulling, that is, working, you'll succeed.
 - The package shipped, i.e. sent, has been returned.
- by adverbs of place, time or mode:
 - In the yard, here, we gather in the evening.
 - At two o'clock, today, we're leaving.
 - Like a cat, lightly, it was walking behind me.

CLASSIFICATION OF THE APPPOSITION

There are different criteria for classifying the apposition, each denoting its particularities:

From a morphological point of view, i.e. according to the part of speech through which it is expressed, the apposition can be nounally, adjectival, numerally, pronominal, verbal and adverbial. The predominant realization of the apposition is the nominal one, where we distinguish two types of appositions: equative and attributive. The common feature is that both are nominal determinants of a nonrestrictive type, are separated from the base by a pause, which is usually marked with a comma. The difference is in terms of syntactic and semantic features, which are different.

a) Equative apposition

This apposition is a secondary predicate placed after the base, which has the role of taking over the attributions of the base by reversing the topic. The basis of this apposition is a nominal group, which can have as its center a common noun (Old house, a ruin, was sold), a proper noun (Ionel, a colleague of Maria, had an accident), a pronoun (I met with her, with your colleague) or a substitute numeral (Only two came, Gigel and Vlad).

The same can be said about the equative apposition, which can be expressed by the same morphological units as the basis:

- common noun-Andrada, his sister, did not come today.
- pronoun - My colleague, that is, he, goes to the delegation.
- substitute numeral - Among the participants, Ioana, the third, was accepted.

As regards the agreement in case of equitable and basic apposition, it is optional, the apposition may resume the case of the first term or may remain in the form of a nominative:

- He addressed Vlad, his colleague.
- He addressed Vlad, his colleague.

b) Attributive apposition

The basis of the attributive apposition is a nominal group that can have as center a common noun (I present to you my colleague, photographer), a pronoun (In the first section I participated with Ionel: he, writer, I, editor) or a numeral (The three, two men and a woman, disappeared into the distance). The difference between the attributive apposition and the base is that the first is realized as a nominal group whose center can only be a common noun without an article, but which is accompanied by determinates when it is part of a statement (My colleague, of Serbian origin, participated in a scientific communication session). The attributive apposition retains a fixed form of nominative, not allowing the agreement in case with the base, as it happened at the equative apposition (The medal was handed to Ștefan Popescu, master of the Popular School of Art). The concept of actants is defined in "structural" syntax (1959): "actors are beings or objects which, in a certain quality and in some way, even as mere extras in the most passive, participates in the process". The Latin origin of easily intuitively driving term, having as reference point the verb "actare, actavi, actatum," from which "actans, actantis"- "acting" is now the active participle².

From a structural point of view:

Depending on whether or not complex the appositional structure is, we distinguish two types of appositions: simple and complex or chained.

a) The simple apposition has a binary structure, the two components that are involved in the equivalence relation and that are compatible with the quality of the group center status

being accompanied by determinants or determinatives, only optionally (Motru, a tiny city, organizes a veritable festival). Although it is a simple apposition, the basis is explained by a developed structure, specified or paraphrased (Her brother, a second-year student at the Police Academy, gave up).

b) Regarding the complex or chained apposition, we are dealing with specific particularities, referring to the base, which has a list-type interpretation. The defining elements for the entity in question are extracted through an identification mechanism, specific to the appositive's relationship, from a number of variables (Mirela, Raluca's sister, student of "Spiru Haret" high school, was awarded).

The apposition has a broader ability to synthesize or explain the informational content of the database. From this point of view, we distinguish the summary apposition and the multiple or analytical apposition.

a) The summary apposition is the one that resumes, usually only through a term, a sequence of coordinated units, units representing the base. This single term can be generic, having associative value (anything, anyone, everything) or private (nothing).

After the fire, they had lost their clothes, their furniture, everything.

Children need parents, teachers, anyone who can guide them.

He had no house, no meal/table, nothing.

b) In the case of multiple or analytical apposition we are dealing with a reverse situation to that of the summary apposition. Here the base is represented as a whole that has been decomposed into component, autonomous, heterogeneous units and which are linked together by a coordination relationship.

The entire hall: parents, teachers, students attended the show.

From a semantical point of view:

This is about the semantic relationship of equivalence, and depending on it, three appositive types are delineated: identification, designation and reformulation.

a) The identification apposition is intended to reveal the identity of the extralinguistic reality, which is expressed on the basis and whose semantic content, most often, is indefinite.

He had six puppies: two black and four white.

b) Designation apposition - here the apposition has a lower degree of specificity than the basis, which it changes and presents the reality that was previously lexically expressed. This position is the inverse of the identification position.

Ioana, my best friend, was gone.

c) The reformulation apposition merely reinterprets the lexical base, both components being determined to the same degree. Here, in our place, it is very pleasant.

APPOSITIVE RELATIONS MARKS

The apposition can be presented in a statement through a series of prosodic or graphic lexical-semantic marks.

Adverbial apposition

The apposition can be marked by lexicons at the lexical-semantic level. Apposes are adverbs with a metalinguistic function that have the role of explaining the appositive relation. Example: in other words, more like, more precisely, better said, namely, respectively, that is, or.

Your non-involvement, more like your disinterest, bothered him.

Of the adverbs listed, some have a relatively free topic, having the possibility to precede the apposition unit or to stand after it (i.e.) and others have fixed topic, always preceding the apposition unit (certainly, such as, respectively, as, or). Each of these appositions is used at a specific semantic ratio between the apposed unit and the base. As a basis for the definition of pragmasemantice for actantului choice for the role of subject² of sentence taking the particularities of pragmatic emphasis of the speaker, decisive role in the distribution of semantic sentence structure in general, and in choosing actantului for the role of the subject, in particular, and, as a consequence, the role of the subject.

The adverb i.e. is used to mark the identification and specification apposition. The adverbs i.e., that is, certainly stand before the apposition that identifies a person or an object (He had only one brother, that is, Vlad). The analytical apposition, with the role of completely indicating the parts of a whole, is indicated by the elements: such as, like, for example, for instance (Common nouns refer to the objects of the same kind, for example, girl, river, table). The actor gives the category empty actants consistency. „The passing from a plan to another is imperceptible³”.

Sentential appositions characterize the popular and familiar spoken language. These are represented by a certain type of sentences, such as: I would say, I would have said, I would say, I would have said, how to say, how to say, how to say, like, so to speak .

Some qualities, such as modesty and inner beauty, are rarely encountered.

Phrasal appositions are characteristic of the same type of language, but they are represented by certain types of incidental phrases: I mean, I mean, I should say, I should say better, I should have said.

Waiting, I mean impatience, drove him mad.

The isolation of the apposition

The apposition can be isolated or uninsulated. Only certain categories of appositions are isolated, considering the particularities of each. Isolate:

a) simple appositions that refer to a pronoun or a proper name (She, Ioana, is my sister)

b) the developed apposition, without considering the part of speech to which it refers and the place occupied in the sentence (Ion Creangă, one of our great classics, left us a real cultural fortune).

Here we have a few points to make: if the developed appositions clear each other up and chained in the sentence, then the appositions are isolated (Ioana, dean's daughter, a hard-working and smart girl, had not come). The appositions which refer to a vocation and stand after it shall also be isolated.

a) the appositions that are introduced by the words: or, that is, namely, or, a.k.a., nicknamed, called (I saw Mihai, a.k.a. the shepherd; He liked a girl, named Stefania).

Sometimes the element “that is” is not at the beginning of the construction, but at the end of it: It will be forgotten, abandoned that is.

TOPIC AND PUNCTUATION OF THE APPPOSITION

From all the above examples, it appears that the apposition is only after the term to which it refers, which it resumes and specifies. Regarding the punctuation of the apposition,

² ***, *Gramatica Limbii Române II*, Vol II, Ed. Academia Română, Buc, 2005, p. 287, 288.

³ Mirabela Rely Odette CURELAR , *The caragialian fantasy – a paradox of the modernity*, Annals of the „Constantin Brâncuși” University of Târgu Jiu, Letters and Social Sciences Series, Issue 1/2009, p.103

it is known that it is separated from the term to which it refers by a comma. As a basis for the definition of pragmasemantice for actantului choice for the role of subject⁴ of sentence taking the particularities of pragmatic emphasis of the speaker, decisive role in the distribution of semantic sentence structure in general, and in choosing actantului for the role of the subject, in particular, and, as a consequence, the role of the subject.

Stylistic values of the apposition

Depending on the context, the apposition can have different stylistic values:

- “conversion value (when it is repeated by reversing the terms, without changing the meaning):... see! around this instinct revolves the life of mankind... Food and reproduction, reproduction and food. - Mihai Eminescu;

- comparison value (comparative apposition): “People dazzle, larvae in darkness” – Camil Petrescu;

- metaphorical value (metaphorical apposition) - The cricket, a tireless singer of the summer days, had fallen silent exhausted under the shadow of the protective height of the grasses - C. Hogăș;

- synecdochally value: And you gather your long blonde hair to the weeping eyes,/ Heart without hope, soul beaten by thought - Mihai Eminescu;

- epithet value - Later, the blue azure, this eternal barrier of human sight, seemed to mean the undisturbed boundaries between the kingdom of the eye and imagination. - C. Hogăș”.

This apposition is a special type of secondary but appositive predicate, which is necessarily placed after the base and can only be substituted for it by suppressing the initial appositive relation.

⁴ ***, *Gramatica Limbii Române II*, Vol II, Ed. Academia Română, Buc, 2005, p. 287, 288.

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3. *Gramatica Limbii Române II*, Vol II, Ed. Academia Română, Buc, 2005, p. 287, 288